

02. Three Odes Dedicated to Küçük Hüseyin Pasha, Foster Brother of Sultan Selim III

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Abstract

Küçük Hüseyin Pasha was the foster brother of Sultan Selim III and one of the men very much close to him. Being brought to an important position (chief admiralty) at a considerably young age, Hüseyin Pasha tried to do his utmost for almost 12 years despite the suspicions and rumours circling around his name. There have been found three odes written by different poets, on the occasion of his inauguration as the chief admiral and the evacuation of Egypt from the invading French forces in his last years. All of those three pieces come across in the Ottoman Archives were included among his inheritance and may have possible been transferred to the palace following his demise. In this study, I tried to give information about the life of the pasha and important instances of his career; additionally, examined the three odes mentioned. Although the expressions in the eulogies do not say anything "new" in terms of the any kind of a novel information regarding the period, they can be considered important from the perspective that they should be included in the authors' works and should be taken into account in the evaluations made related to their poetics.

Keywords: Küçük Hüseyin Pasha, Selim III, ode/qasida, chief admiral, poetics

Sultan III. Selim'in Sütkardeşine İthaf Edilen Üç Kaside

Öz

Küçük Hüseyin Pařa, Sultan III. Selim'in sütkardeři ve yakın adamlarındandı. Genç yařta kaptan-ı deryalık gibi önemli bir mevkie getirilen pařa, hakkındaki řüphelere ve iltimas dedikodularına rağmen 12 yıl sürdürdüğünü görevini hakkıyla yerine getirmeye çalıştı. Kaptan-ı derya olarak göreve başlayışı ve son yıllarında yürüttüğü Mısır'ın Fransızlardan tahliyesi harekâtı vesilesiyle hakkında üç ayrı şair tarafından kâğda dökülen üç kaside bulundu. Cumhurbaşkanlığı Osmanlı Arşivi'nde tek dosya içerisinde bulunan üç kaside, pařanın vefatının ardından saraya intikal etmiş olması muhtemel terekesinde yer alıyordu. Bu çalışmada pařanın hayatına ve kariyerinin önemli kesitlerine dair bilgi verilmeye çalışıldı; ayrıca sözü edilen üç kaside içerik bakımından değerlendirildi. Kasidelerde yer alan ifadeler dönem bilgisi açısından "yeni" bir şeyler söylemiyorsa da şairlerinin müellefatına dâhil edilmeleri ve poetikasına mahsus değerlendirmelerde göz önünde bulundurulmaları gerekliliği bakımından önemli kabul edilebilir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Küçük Hüseyin Pařa, III. Selim, kaside, kaptan-ı derya, poetika

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1. The Life of Chief Admiral Küçük Hüseyin Pasha

One of the important figures in Ottoman maritime affairs was Hüseyin Pasha, who was known by the nicknames² "Küçük" (small) and "Gazi" (veteran). The sources do not have any information about when Küçük Hüseyin Pasha, who is claimed to be of Georgian or Circassian origin³, was born. However, based on the knowledge that he was forty-six years old when he passed away, he was probably born in 1172 according to the Hijri calendar and 1758/59 according to the Gregorian calendar.⁴ Hüseyin Pasha, who was nicknamed "small" due to his small size, was rewarded with the title of admiral and the dynasty son-in-law after he was presented to Mustafa III by Silahdar Ibrahim Pasha of Akhaltsikhe in 1767-1768. This was the beginning of a turning point that opened the gates of the palace to the pasha, who earned great titles during his short life. Küçük Hüseyin, who first studied in the Enderun (a special school in the Ottoman palace) subsequently went into the service of Şehzade (prince) Mehmed, the brother of Prince Selim. His fate changed on April 7, 1789 when Selim III assumed the throne. After performing his duties as attendant officer and dresser (*mabeynci* and *tebdilci*) in the inner circle of the palace for just 5 or six months, Küçük Hüseyin Agha was appointed chief magistrate. This promotion, which was considered unusual, brought Küçük Hüseyin Agha even closer to Selim III. Hüseyin Agha started to participate in the sultan's engagement drills in Beşiktaş Ihlamur and took part in the efforts of the French ambassador Sebastiani and İshak Bey to reorganize the Ottoman army. This meant that he had earned the affection and appreciation of the sultan. The appointment of Küçük Hüseyin Agha with the rank of vizier on March 10, 1792 to admiral was already a manifestation of the relationship and affection between them. This affection and appreciation was taken one step further; Esmâ Sultan, daughter of Abdülhamid I, and Küçük Hüseyin Pasha were married on 29 May 1792.

The pasha, who was appointed to the rank of admiral with the vizierate, was still in his early 30s. He did not have adequate maritime experience to be admiral. Furthermore, compared to the age of the other pashas who were appointed to the relevant duty at that time⁵, it was hard not to see that the pasha was highly "praised". As a matter of fact, he continued his duty for almost 12 years until his demise at the end of 1803. Despite his relative inexperience, the appointment of Hüseyin Pasha in the navy, where a series of reforms was carried out, was also an indication of the Sultan's confidence in the Pasha.⁶

Ahmed Vasif and Ahmet Cevdet Pasha described Küçük Hüseyin Agha's appointment as a treasurer and translator and his appointment as the chief magistrate five or six months later after the accession of Selim III as contrary to the Enderun order, however there didn't seem to be any irregularities. Hüseyin Agha, who entered the palace at the age of ten, had almost twenty-five years of palace experience until he was appointed to this position. Therefore, the appointment had nothing to do with favour or coincidence.⁷

² Another nickname the pasha had was "tayazade". This nickname was given on the grounds that he and Sultan Selim III were raised by the same caregiver/wet nurse. Danişmend, *İzahlı Kronolojik Osmanlı Tarihi*, V, 2011, (İstanbul: Doğu Kütüphanesi): 264.

³ In the 5th volume of Chronology, Danişmend writes that Ata Bey is of Georgian descent, referring to his history. Danişmend, *a.g.e.*, V, 2011, (İstanbul: Doğu Kütüphanesi): 264.

⁴ Nejad Göyünç, "Kapudan-ı Derya Küçük Hüseyin Paşa", *İ.Ü. Edebiyat Fakültesi Tarih Dergisi*, (II) 3-4: 35.

⁵ For comparison with his predecessors such as Melek Mehmed Pasha and Gazi Hasan Pasha, see Danişmend, *a.g.e.*, V, 260-64. Despite the aforementioned favor clause, Zinkeisen implies and claims that the pasha was on a level with his predecessor, Gazi Hasan Pasha, and that he facilitated the sultan's work in reforms. See Johann Wilhelm Zinkeisen, *Osmanlı İmparatorluğu Tarihi VI*, (İstanbul: Yeditepe, 2011), 25.

⁶ Mustafa Nuri Paşa, *Netâyicü'l-Vukuât*, (ed. Neşet Çağatay), (Ankara: TTK Basımevi, 1987), 197.

⁷ Ertan Ünlü, "Kaptan-ı Derya Küçük Hüseyin Paşa'nın Gelirleri ve Giderleri", *TAD*, (40) 69: 237.

The first action that Küçük Hüseyin Pasha, who was the admiral, who had climbed the career ladder and reached the state of being a groom in the dynasty in the Ottoman palace, which he had entered as a "servant" who could reach the sultan's closest, was to fight against the pirates in the Aegean Sea. The primary task of Küçük Hüseyin Pasha was to solve this problem that harmed the state and the nation. In any case, after marrying Esmâ Sultan, the pasha took to the sea in June 1792 without having a wedding.

As Göyünç (1999: 6-7) points out, Hüseyin Pasha's activities during his tenure as admiral can be evaluated under four headings. His primary job was the fight against pirates in the Aegean Sea. At this time, there were many pirates in the Aegean Sea, some of whom sailed under the Russian flag who prevented the navigation of Ottoman merchant ships, looted them and raided the coasts. As soon as Küçük Hüseyin Pasha took over the task, he went to sea focusing on two pirates who were particularly distinguished: Lambro and Karakaçan. These successes, which he achieved in a short time, pleased the sultan and made his peers uneasy.

In the second place was Vidin's activities during his seraskerat. Pazvandođlu Osman had tried to take control of Vidin, which had become a nest of rebels after 1794, but had not been successful. In November 1797, the General Assembly, which gathered in the Sublime Porte, decided to take Pazvandođlu down. Thereupon, Küçük Hüseyin Pasha was appointed serasker to Vidin on 1 December 1797. His rivals, who wanted him out of Istanbul, were influential in this appointment and thought that his reputation would be diminished if he failed. When Napoleon landed in Egypt in July 1798, Hüseyin Pasha was recalled. Thereupon, Hüseyin Pasha conveyed Pazvandođlu Osman's request for amnesty to the centre and had him pardoned despite the death penalty he had been given. Thus, this issue was also resolved, and the pasha returned to Istanbul in January 1799.

His third activity was around the Egyptian issue. Küçük Hüseyin Pasha returned from Vidin and sailed to the Mediterranean with his navy, and joined the British navy, which was blockading the Egyptian coasts. However, despite the blockade, Napoleon's clandestine escape to France in August 1799 could not be prevented. A treaty was signed with the French in 1801. Egyptian scholars gathered at the Kansu Gavri Palace in Cairo and a khutbah (sermon) of conquest was recited on behalf of Selim III. The keys of the castle were sent to Istanbul. Hüseyin Pasha's efforts and successes here made Sultan Selim very satisfied.

The most important activity of Hüseyin Pasha that can be mentioned in the fourth group were the reforms made in the navy. In this context, first he made some changes in the shipyard and navy. Reforms were carried out on many topics such as ensuring that the navy crew remained in the shipyard during all four seasons and continued their training, categorizing the navy captains according to their qualifications, preventing the demoting of those who were not at fault, creating a master-apprentice class by including carpenters among the navy regulars, and separating the galleons into large and small ones. Jacques Balthazard le Brun, the French naval architect whose expertise in shipbuilding is widely accepted in line with the importance he attaches to education, was brought to Istanbul with his two assistants, Jean-Baptiste Benoît and Toussaint Petit. Significant progress was made in training and shipbuilding technology under the leadership of the French team. Forty-five new warships were added to the Ottoman navy between 1789 and 1798. The firepower of the navy reached 2156 guns and the number of troops reached 40,000. Thus, the Ottoman navy became one of the strongest navies in Europe. Turkish engineers trained with le Brun at the Naval Engineering House in Hasköy and

subsequently assigned to other shipyards. Several pools were built in the shipyard, and the Shipyard Palace was also repaired.

While these activities in the navy were continuing, in November 1803, the pasha fell ill with tuberculosis. He must have felt that he was going to die because he wrote and submitted a testament to Sultan III. His wife loved luxury and he was also quite extravagant himself. Referring to this situation, Cevdet Pasha used a sarcastic expression for himself as “nehhâb u vehhâb” (a generous spoiler). Therefore, first he asked the ruler for the payment of his debts and asked for the sale of his goods. After a short period of time, he passed away on 8 December 1803 and was buried next to the Mihrişah Valide Sultan Tomb in Eyüp. The historian Vâsif commemorated his demise with the verse “Gülşen-i Adn ola mesken Kapudan Paşa'ya”.

2. Three Odes by Three Poets

It is known that the odes were a kind of continuation of the verses sung to praise the khans or beys that existed with the ancient Turks. The odes, which became a part of the Turkish divan literature samples, the first examples of which were seen in the 14th century, were written to praise the Prophet and other religious leaders, a contemporary of the poet, written for reasons such as praying to Allah, asking for intercession from the Prophet, requesting a civil service from a statesman, and a desire to be protected. In this context, Küçük Hüseyin Pasha was also a name for whom odes were written, as he was a remarkable figure of the period and "from whom rank was sought " due to his closeness to the sultan.

Some odes were written and presented to him on both his appointment and the superiority achieved against the French army in Egypt. The three odes published for the first time with this work were poems by Sürurî, Yüsrî and Rıza Efendi, respectively. Although Sururi had a divan and most of the historical couplets have been entered, this ode, which was found in the Ottoman archives of the Presidency, was not included in any of his works, nor was it seen and published in the next period.

The aforementioned ode of Sürurî dates back to 1207 when he was appointed to the post of admiral.⁸ In the ode, which consists of 20 couplets, Sürurî included concepts specific to the sea and maritime, such as “stock, anchor, sail, harbor and bahr”. At the end of the ode, Süruri said that he depicted two historical lines pointing to the same date:

“Ey Sürurî iki tarih-i dil-âvîz dedim / Döktü korsanı bozup bahre Kapudan Paşa
Cenk ile salb-i ‘adûdan alıcak peygâmı / Sek gibi astı tutup Karakaçan-ı bed-nâmı”

Sururi, who started his ode by praising Sultan Selim, said, "He has made a special ode to me / It is a gift of fate by acting on his glory". He emphasized that the sultan had appointed his subject as admiral by saying “Kıldı bir bende-i hâsın kapudân-ı deryâ / Şânına eyleyüp emvâc-ı kader ikrâmı”, and “a waves of fate lapping to his glory”. Referring to his bravery and bravery, Süruri pointed out that the pasha had transformed the Mediterranean sea into the Black sea with the smoke of gunpowder with the couplet “Dûd-ı barutla Deryâ-yı Sefid’i şimdî / Etti a’dâ gözüne Bahr-i Siyâh ikdâmı”.

With the lines “Cenk ile salb-i ‘adûdan alıcak peygâmı” and “Sek gibi astı tutup Karakaçan-ı bed-nâmı” at the end of the ode, Sürurî both states that he hanged the enemy/pirate (Lambro) captured by the

⁸ BOA. TS.MA.e 683/16-3.

pasha and Karakaçan, who was also a pirate in the Aegean Sea he further refers to the year 1207 when Küçük Hüseyin Pasha was appointed admiral.

Yüsri also referred to the successes he achieved in the Aegean Sea in the first period of his duty when he was appointed to (Emr-i bahri edüp i'tâ Hüseyin Paşa'ya / Kapudân eyledi ol şâh-ı kerâmet-disâr).⁹ Yüsri preferred to use a heavier language compared to the ode of Süruri.

Even though he referred to the inexperience of Hüseyin Pasha, Yüsri appreciated the courageous march of Hüseyin Pasha against the pirates as soon as he took over the task by saying, "Hayder-i ruz-ı vega ya'ni Kapudan Paşa / Sâhib-i seyf ü ilm mahî-i küfr u küffâr" and compared the pasha to Prophet Ali by describing him as both "the valiant man of the war day" and as the holder of a pen/knowledge equipped with a sword.

He points out the benefits the pasha has achieved by saying,

"Bozdu hem düşmeni hem ahz-ı sefâyin etti / Öyle bir cenk ü sitiz eyledi kim sihr-âsâr
Kılup âvîze ser-i düşmen olan bed-kârı / Kuvvet-i kâhiresin etti o demde izhâr"

In other words, he destroyed the enemy and captured their ships, and that he fought as if by magic. He also pointed out that the pirate, who was leading the enemy troops, "hung" his head like a chandelier, claiming that this was a sign of his devastating power.

The text written by Rıza Efendi was a pentastich.¹⁰ He refers to the event in which the invading Egyptian army was expelled from the country, that the "restitute" experienced with the phrase "Hüve'l-Fettah" in the title can be considered a kind of conquest, but the real conqueror/conquest is Allah.

The eulogy, consisting of five stanzas in the form of *müselles*, also had a repeating refrain couplet. The general theme of the poem, as mentioned above, was about the "conquest of Egypt by ship". Presumably, with this "ship" record, Rıza was referring to the conquest Sultan Selim I from land. Egypt was conquered again with the rumbling cannons of the pasha, who came to Egypt with the ships dancing on the sea, and his grace and benevolence reminiscent of the Nile became the reason for the revival of the Egyptian soil. In addition, with these achievements, as in the ode of Pasha Süruri, both Prophet Ali and Sultan III, whom he describes as İskender-i Sâni (Alexander II) as a result of his heroics he was seen as the "Âsaf" of Selim III, that is, his closest man/deputy:

"Ruh-ı tedbîrde bir cevher-i sâni gibidir
Ey Rızâ, âsaf-ı İskender-i sâni gibidir
Hem şecâ'atte bakın Haydar-ı sâni gibidir."

3. Transliteration of The Odes

Tarih Muzaffer-şüden-i Kapudan Paşa

Şurta-i avn-i Hudâ eyledi pür-cüş-ı safâ
Kulzüm-i tab'-ı güher-zâ-yı şeh-i İslâm'ı

⁹ BOA. TS.MA.e 683/16-2.

¹⁰ BOA. TS.MA.e 683/16-4.

Ya'nî Sultan Selim Hân ki yemm-i irfânda
Muhtevîdir sadef-i kalbi dürr-i ilhâmı

Zıkr-i temkini güzâr etse leb-i deryâda
Mevcler nakş-ı hacir veş bulur istihkâmı

Sûy-ı merâ-yı merama cereyân etmededir
Rûzigârında bulup felek fülk-i eyyâmı

Kıldı bir bende-i hâsın kapudân-ı deryâ
Şânına eyleyüp emvâc-ı kader ikrâmı

Ziynet-i felek-celâdet Hüseyin Paşa kim
Rûz-ı hîcâda donanmadır anın bayramı

Himmet-i mâlin bahrine o düstür-ı cesur
Mazhariyetle hemî oldu muhit ahkâmı

Yedi deryaya vizân eylese bâd-ı gadabın
Kemterin mevcesi gark eyleye heft ecrâmı

Keştî-i şöhreti yelken açalı deryâda
Battu lenger gibi korsân-ı la'înin nâmı

Dûd-ı barutla Deryâ-yı Sefid'i şimdi
Etti a'dâ gözüne Bahr-i Siyâh ikdâmı

Aştı emvâc-ı kerem askerinin başından
Cûş edüp vakt-i tesâdüfte yemm-i in'âmı

Hasmı limanda işittükte hücum etti guzât
Kalmayup bahr-i hurûşân gibi ârâmı

İsteyüp Karakaçan meyl-i kenâr etse 'adû
Zor kande dolaşırdu resne ikdâmı

Kaçsa gülle yetişür, dursa gemisi tutuşur
Vire ile n'ola eylerse nigûn i'lâmı

Çifte kule iki müřt-i ecel idi hasma
Teknelerde n'ola yoęruldu ise endâmı

Hayli aktarma alup ceng-ile pařa-yı dilir
Hep esir eyledi ol tâ'ife-i hod-kâmı

Bir kaçan cundaya salb eyleyüp ol kelblerin
Mücib-i fitnenin oldu sebab-i i'dâmı

Böyle hemvâra Huda Nuh nebî hürmetine
Ceyř-i a'dâsını mâhî ola kendin hâmî

Ey **Sürûri** iki tarih-i dil-âvîz dedim
Cenk ile salb-i 'adûdan alıcak peygâmı

Döktü korsamı bozup bahre Kapudan Pařa
Sek gibi astı tutup Karakaçan-ı bed-nâmı

1207

[te]mm[e]

Li-muharririhî'l-Âciz

Şeh-i Fârûk-şiyem hazret-i Sultan Selim
Gülşen-i adl ü kerem gülbün-i gülzâr-ı bahâr
Vâye-bahş-ı ümerâ nâzım-ı silk-i ulemâ
Hâmî-i dîn-i mübîn dâd-ger-i adl-âsâr
Emr-i bahri edüp i'tâ Hüseyin Pařa'ya
Kapudân eyledi ol şâh-ı kerâmet-disâr
Nâsiyesinde müşâhid idi ikbâl ü zafer
Yümnile oldu donanma-yı hümayuna süvâr
Etti azm-i reh-i maksûd kıldı muzaffer
Nazar-ı pâdişeh-i dâd-kirdâr-ı dü yâr
Hayder-i rûz-ı vegâ ya'nî Kapudan Pařa
Sâhib-i seyf ü ilim mâhî-i küfr ü küffâr
Top-ı ejder u menk sadme-i âşûbundan
Pür-tanîn oldu o dem tas-ı sipihr-i devvâr
Bozdu hem düşmeni hem ahz-ı sefâyin etti
Öyle bir cenk ü sitiz eyledi kim sihr-âsâr
Kılup âvîze ser-i düşmen olan bed-kârı
Kuvvet-i kâhiresin etti o demde izhâr
Bu gazâ ile meserrette iken cümle enâm

Adres

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Müjde-i seher-i hümâyûn olıcağ gûş-güzâr
 Bârekallâh zihî kevkebe-i ferr u haşmet
 Oldu mesrur bütün halk-ı cihân diğeri yâr
 Oldu tertîb-i alay rûz-ı ferah-tev'emde
 Geldi hep şevk u meserret girü kaldı ekdâr
 Ya'nî pişinde divân-ı cümle kibâr-ı devlet
 Bir alay oldu ki tevfiğ idi hatta dümdâr
 Dîde-i düşmene mil çekti sûtûnu gördüm
 Ber-keşîde olan ol surda nahl-i zertâr
 Burc-ı şevketten olup tâli' o mâh-ı tâbân
 Oldu hurşîde bu şeb beyt-i şeref-cây karâr
 İzz ü iclâl ile hûrân u kusûr-ı cennet
 Mün'akis âyine-i hacle-gühende didâr
 Sözü kasr eyle yeter eyleme tasdî-i tîr
 Kıl du'â kâvile edâ lâzime-i hakk-ı civâr
 Kâm-kâr ede serîrinde Hudâ-yı bî-çûn
 Re'yi makbul ola çün zümre-i hâss-ı ebrâr
 Düştü bâ-lutf-i Hudâ **Yüsrî** bu târîh-i zifât
 Mihr-i bâlâya karîn oldu meh-i pür-envâr

Hüve'l-Fettâh

Yemm-i lütfun kapudanı Hüseyin Paşa'dır
 Kılıcı çarh-ı şecâ'atte meh-i garrâdır
 Mısr'a evvel giren ol zât-ı güher-âsâdır
 Fetheden fülkle Mısr'ı Hüseyin Paşa'dır
 Nil-i eltâfi o hâke sebep-i ihyadır
 Geldi keştilere bir çünbüş-i Nusret görsen
 Raks eder deryâda misâl-i tûsen
 Evvelâ Mısr'ı alan zât-ı kerîm der isen
 Fetheden fülkle Mısr'ı Hüseyin Paşa'dır
 Nil-i eltâfi o hâke sebep-i ihyadır
 Sinesi güm güm eder topların şu kanden
 Raks eder eşhebi esb-i Mısrî zevkinden
 Bellüdüdür sıdkı şehi rast-rehe sevkinden
 Fetheden fülkle Mısr'ı Hüseyin Paşa'dır
 Nil-i eltâfi o hâke sebep-i ihyadır
 Kand-i vasfın eder iken ele alsam hâme
 Döner ol lezzet ile çüb-ı nebât şâme
 Sadr-ı a'zam dedi hünkâra yazup bir nâme
 Fetheden fülkle Mısr'ı Hüseyin Paşa'dır

Nîl-i eltâfi o hâke sebeb-i ihyadır
 Ruh-ı tedbîrde bir cevher-i sâni gibidir
 Ey **Rızâ**, âsaf-ı İskender-i sâni gibidir
 Hem şecâ'atte bakın Haydar-ı sâni gibidir
 Fetheden fülkle Mısır'ı Hüseyin Paşa'dır
 Nîl-i eltâfi o hâke sebeb-i ihyadır.

Conclusion

Küçük Hüseyin Pasha, despite his young age, was a figure that Sultan Selim III, who was considered the "enlightened despot" of the 18th century trusted and brought to the head of an important unit such as the navy based on this trust. The fact that they had grown up together at the sultan's choice, mutual trust and the determined character of the pasha must have been effective. As a matter of fact, he became the trigger and maintainer of important moves in the navy together with the pasha sultan, who remained in the position of admiral for almost 12 years until his demise at an early age (46). His appointment to office and the successes he achieved during his duty were the subject of odes by the poets of the period, who wanted to gain both appreciation and acceptance. Although there is information about Süruri and Rıza whose odes are mentioned in the study and who are considered to be important poets of the 18-19th century, we could not come across a "Yüsrî" who lived in 1792, which is thought to have been the year the odes were written. In this context, it is estimated that this Yusri was a different personality from his predecessors who shared the same pen name. In addition, it can be argued that the three odes in the Ottoman archives have not been published anywhere before, that they can constitute an addendum to the works of the relevant poets, and that they represent an important piece of evidence with their expressions and contents.

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